

NUMERICAL DESIGN OPTIMISATION OF A COMPOSITE REACTION LINK

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1 Introduction

Advanced composite materials such as Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) can provide high strength-to-weight ratio, combined with high corrosion resistance, desirable fatigue performance and excellent tailorable characteristics compared to metals. These properties are very attractive to the aerospace industry, leading to an increasing demand for replacement of metallic parts with advanced composite material. Optimisation of composite structures has become a key stage in the design of prototypes. It is often a challenge to design a composite component to meet the required structural performance with a significantly reduced weight. With an optimised design, the product can show significantly higher strength to weight ratios; however, a poor design could produce a heavier, more expensive and lower quality product. Numerical modelling is therefore often required to optimise composite structures in terms of weight reduction and/or strength [1, 2] increase. The type of fibre, stacking sequence, and geometrical dimensions of composite structures are commonly taken as design variables for tailoring and improving the structural performance of the product.

Before the early 21st century, most research on optimisation of composite structures was restricted to structures with a simple geometry, such as plates and beams, [3, 4] due to the mathematical complexity involved. Currently, advanced finite element analysis (FEA) tools make it possible to optimise complex composite structures [5, 6].

The design optimisation process and the full-scale testing results for a composite reaction link are presented in this paper. This reaction link is part of the aileron control system of the Boeing 777 aircraft,

which adjusts the aircraft's flight attitude. The reaction link was originally made of titanium alloy. Using composite material has the potential to offer significant weight saving over the original metallic reaction link. The objective of this work is to design and optimise the composite fibre lay-up for the reaction link to satisfy specified strength and service deformation requirements.

The optimisation was limited by spatial restrictions. The design of the reaction link was also influenced by the manufacturing process, which had to be simple and cost effective.

2 Approach

2.1 Geometry

The configuration of the FEA model is shown in Figure 1. A removable metallic arm is attached to the composite reaction link by a metallic pin. The metallic head is locked into position by two insert plates. The main composite body consists of two sections; section A and B.

Figure 1 Configuration of the FEA model.

2.2 Software

Abaqus 6.11-3 was used for this project.

2.3 Lay-up

A two-dimensional (2D), gradient descent, Newton-Raphson method was derived for implicit FEA-based optimisation of the composite lay-up. To fully test this approach to composite optimization, the choice of fabrics was restricted to $\pm 45^\circ$ woven and 0° unidirectional (UD) plies. The ply angles are defined relatively to the U_2 axis (Figure 1).

Two design variables were selected to characterise the design:

- r denotes the fraction of $\pm 45^\circ$ woven composite in the section A (See Figure 1);
- ρ denotes the fraction of woven $\pm 45^\circ$ composite in the section B (See Figure 1).

A single objective function, Φ_1 was defined as:

$$\Phi_1 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_u}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta_{max}}{\delta_L}\right)^2$$

where σ_{max} is the maximum stress, and δ_{max} is the maximum leg deflection (both obtained from the FEA), σ_u is the ultimate strength, and δ_L is the required deflection limit. To minimise the objective function, a 2D gradient-descent was employed. The approach was to start with initially $r = \rho = 0.5$.

Given a point $x_K = (r_K, \rho_K)$ in the design space, the next point in the Newton-Raphson update is defined as:

$$x_{K+1} = x_K - H[\Phi(x_k)]^{-1} \nabla \Phi(x_k)$$

H is the Hessian matrix of second order partial derivatives. To compute a single Newton-Raphson update, six distinct simulations are required to approximate the gradient and the Hessian.

Letting α represent either σ or δ , the following notation was used:

Figure 2 Loading and boundary conditions.

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{00} &= \alpha(r, \rho) & ; & \alpha_{-10} = \alpha(r - \Delta r, \rho) \\ \alpha_{10} &= \alpha(r + \Delta r, \rho) & ; & \alpha_{-01} = \alpha(r, \rho - \Delta \rho) \\ \alpha_{01} &= \alpha(r, \rho + \Delta \rho) & ; & \alpha_{11} = \alpha(r + \Delta r, \rho + \Delta \rho) \end{aligned}$$

where, Δr and $\Delta \rho$ are the iteration step size, which are initially set to 0.1.

Two inequality constraints were set in the design space. They are: $0 \leq r \leq 1$, and $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$. Elastic analyses with different stacking sequences were carried out to determine the optimal composite lay-up design. To check that a local minimum is not given by this gradient method, 15 more analyses were carried out with different starting points in the design space.

To check the sensitivity of the composite lay-up to the selected objective function, the following two additional objective functions were selected.

$$\Phi_2 = \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_u}\right) + \left(\frac{\delta_{max}}{\delta_L}\right) \right]^2$$

$$\Phi_3 = 0.75 \left(\frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_u}\right)^3 + 0.25 \left(\frac{\delta_{max}}{\delta_L}\right)^3$$

In Φ_2 , the design variables are coupled. In Φ_3 , weighting factors were applied; hence, it is a more stress dominated optimisation.

2.4 Loading and boundary conditions

The loading and boundary conditions for the FEA models are shown in Figure 2. The loading pin which connects to the metallic head is coupled to a reference point, and it is constrained in the x and z directions ($U_1 = U_3 = 0$). A tensile and compressive load was applied to this point. The fixed pin, which joins the composite legs, is coupled to another reference point, and is constrained in the x, y and z directions ($U_1 = U_2 = U_3 = 0$). Frictionless contact was used at the loading pin/fixed pin joint. Frictional contact of 0.05 was chosen at the pin and metallic arm to add friction to the model and aid convergence. The same contact condition was applied at the contact between composite and pin.

2.5 Mesh

The model was meshed with a combination of linear 8-node 3D brick elements (type C3D8R in Abaqus), and 3D linear tetrahedron elements (type C3D4). In total, the numerical model has 102621 elements. The composite stacking direction is also indicated in Figure 3, where the orange colour shows the top surfaces.

Figure 3 Mesh of the reaction link model.

2.6 Optimisation process

A two-dimensional (2D), gradient descent, Newton-Raphson method was applied to minimise the maximum principal stress and the maximum displacement of the legs under service load using objective function Φ_1 . This process converged after a few loops, when the point in the parameter space became essentially stationary. In total, 45 analyses were conducted. The results have been interpolated with a nearest neighbour approach and plotted in Figure 4. As mentioned in Section 2.3, two additional functions were selected to assess the sensitivity of the results to the objective function.

Figures 5 and 6 shows that all three objective functions indicate almost the same optimal composite lay-up.

Figure 4 3D plot of objective function Φ_1 .

Figure 5 3D plot of objective function Φ_2 .

Figure 6 3D plot of objective function Φ_3 .

2.7 Stress and strain analyses

Stress and strain analyses were conducted for each numerical model. The reaction link under tensile load is more highly stressed than under compressive load. For the final reaction link, high stress regions in the composite part appear near the edge of the top and bottom surfaces of the composite shoulder section in contact with the metallic head part, and at the area around the pin hole (Figure 7). Figure 8 shows that the strain concentrations are at similar regions, circled in red.

Figure 7 Stress distribution of the reaction link model with optimal composite lay-up, under tensile load.

Figure 8 Strain distribution of the reaction link model with optimal composite lay-up, under tensile load.

3 Manufacturing and testing

The Reaction Link lay-up was deduced from the objective functions, giving the best ratio of $\pm 45^\circ$ woven and 0° UD for the sections A and B. The lay-up was fairly simple, knowing the thickness of each ply and the total thickness of the section A and B. The lay-up was designed to be symmetric and balanced.

Manufacturing of the reaction link was carried out in two main steps. First, the section B was laid-up and cured, and then the section A was applied and cured while mounted in a second tool. Once cured, the metallic (titanium in this case) head and leg were mounted on the part. The final reaction link sample is shown in Figure 9.

Four full-scale specimens of the new reaction link with the optimised composite lay-up were fabricated at TWI, and were tested up to 100kN tensile and compressive load (Figure 10). Testing consisted of alternating compressive and tensile loads at various incremental loads ($\pm 66\text{kN}$, $\pm 80\text{kN}$ and $\pm 100\text{kN}$).

Figure 9 Final reaction link.

Figure 10 Reaction link load/displacement test.

The part passed the $\pm 100\text{kN}$ threshold without any visible or audible signs of delamination.

The numerical model was validated, and the new design of reaction link with the optimised composite lay-up satisfies the service requirements.

4 Conclusions

A 2D, gradient descent, Newton-Raphson method was applied for implicit FEA-based optimisation of the composite lay-up, in order to minimise the maximum principal stress and deflection of the composite leg. Based on the numerical analyses, the contour of the objective function was obtained. By finding the minimum value of this objective function, the optimal design of composite lay-up was achieved.

The two-step manufacturing process proved to be time-efficient, simple to use and gave the part a smooth surface finish. The final part has also satisfied both design and mechanical requirements.

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